

Comparison of clinical performance of Guardian Laryngeal Mask Airway Verses Supreme Laryngeal Mask Airway

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Abstract

Background: The Guardian Laryngeal Mask Airway (G-LMA) is a new extra glottic device, silicone-based, single-use, with a cuff pilot valve with pressure indicator and an integrated gastric drainage port. We aimed to compare the clinical performance of this laryngeal mask airway with the Supreme Laryngeal Mask Airway (S-LMA) in paralyzed, anesthetized adult patients. **Material and methods:** In this prospective, randomized study, we recruited 80 adult patients scheduled for an elective surgical procedure under total intravenous anaesthesia in a supine position. The patients were randomly distributed into two groups, with 40 patients in each group - Group G and Group S, where G-LMA and S-LMA were used respectively. The cuff of each device was inflated with air to 60 cmH₂O. The primary aim of this study was to compare the airway sealing pressure of S-LMA and G-LMA. The secondary aim was to compare the efficacy and safety of these two laryngeal mask airway devices in terms of successful insertion, insertion time, successful insertion of a gastric tube, gastric tube insertion time, volume of air for cuff inflation to 60 cmH₂O, intracuff pressure measurement, fiber-optic position of airway assessment, and postoperative pharyngolaryngeal adverse events. **Results:** At 60 cmH₂O intracuff pressure, the airway sealing pressure of G-LMA was higher than S-LMA ($p=0.003$). The volume of air for cuff inflation was less in G-LMA than S-LMA ($p=0.03$). We found no differences in both groups with respect to the first successful insertion attempt ($p=1.000$), device insertion time ($p=0.530$), first successful insertion attempt for gastric tube placement ($p=1.000$), gastric tube insertion time ($p=0.111$), fiber-optic position of airway devices ($p=0.437$), intracuff pressure at 30, 60, 90, and 120 minutes ($p=0.272, 0.327, 0.589, 0.469$), blood staining ($p=0.578$). The postoperative pharyngolaryngeal adverse events at 1, 2, and 24 hours after the end of surgery were comparable. **Conclusion:** The Guardian laryngeal mask airway provides better airway sealing pressure at 60 cmH₂O cuff pressure during controlled ventilation than the Supreme laryngeal mask airway.

Keywords: Guardian laryngeal mask airway, Supreme laryngeal mask airway, Ambu cuff pressure gauge.

Background:

Laryngeal Mask Airway (LMA) is an extraglottic airway device that was invented and designed by Dr. Archie Brain in 1981. It was clinically approved by the US Food and Drug Administration in 1991. Difficult intubation remains an important cause of anaesthetic morbidity and mortality. The immediately life-threatening situation occurs as "cannot intubate, cannot ventilate"[1]. Dr. Brain changed the scenario from "unable to intubate and ventilate" to "unable to intubate but able to ventilate"[2]. Previously, the primary drawback of LMA is regurgitation of gastric content[3]. To overcome this problem, the extraglottic airway devices have an inbuilt gastric drainage port to facilitate the efflux of gastric content and allow the insertion of a drainage tube. The Guardian Laryngeal Mask Airway (G-LMA) (Ultimate Medical Pty Ltd, Richmond, Vic, Australia) is a new silicone-based single-use extraglottic airway device that forms a seal with the glottis for ventilation and with the hypopharynx for airway protection, and provides a gastric drainage port (Figure 1). In addition, it has a port for suctioning material from the hypopharynx and a pilot balloon valve that constantly monitors intracuff pressure[4]. The Supreme Laryngeal Mask Airway (S-LMA) (The Laryngeal Mask Company, Singapore) is a polyvinyl chloride (PVC)-based single-use extraglottic airway device that facilitates ventilation and provides a gastric drainage port[5,6]. We hypothesized that the difference in cuff design and airway tube results in differing effectiveness of glottis seal for ventilation. The aim of this study is to compare G-LMA vs. S-LMA and their postoperative pharyngolaryngeal adverse events. Our primary outcome of this study was to compare the airway sealing pressure (ASP) of S-LMA and G-LMA, and the secondary outcome was to compare the efficacy and safety of these two LMA devices with regard to successful insertion attempts, device insertion time, successful gastric tube insertion attempts, gastric tube insertion time, volume of air for cuff inflation to 60 cmH₂O, intracuff pressure (ICP) measurement, Fiber-optic position of airway assessment, and postoperative pharyngolaryngeal adverse events.

Material and methods

The study protocol was approved by the Tianjin Medical University General Hospital ethics committee. All patients gave written informed consent prior to the study. This prospective randomized trial was conducted in 80 adult patients with a physical status of American Society of Anaesthesiologists (ASA) grade I and II scheduled for an elective surgical procedure in the supine position within 2 hours of predicted total intravenous anaesthesia. The patients were randomly allocated to two groups: Group G, where G-LMA was used, and group S, where S-LMA was used. Each group had 40 patients. The patient was randomly selected from different surgical departments (gynecology, general surgery, orthopedics, and urology) using the sealed envelope method. Patients younger than 18 years, known difficult airway, pregnancy, body weight less than 50 kg, BMI greater than 35 kg/m², cervical spine disease, incisor distance less than 2.5 cm, thyromental distance less than 6 cm, Mallampatti grading III and IV, recent history of upper respiratory and alimentary tract infection, history of upper gastrointestinal surgery, hiatus hernia, gastroesophageal reflux disease, and full stomach were excluded from the study [7-10]. All the patients were examined during the preoperative visit and asked to fast overnight prior to surgery. Inside the operating room, standard monitors were applied, including pulse oximetry, invasive blood pressure, and electrocardiography. After preoxygenation for 3 minutes, anaesthesia was induced by intravenous administration of Midazolam 0.05mg/kg, Sufentanil 0.4µg/kg, and Propofol 2-2.5mg/kg, followed by Rocuronium 0.6mg/kg as neuromuscular blockade. The patients' lungs were manually ventilated via a facemask with oxygen for 3 minutes using an

anaesthetic machine. Once the adequate depth of anaesthesia was achieved, absence of motor response to jaw thrust [11], an assigned LMA was inserted in either group of patients. The G-LMA was inserted using the digital insertion technique in the sniffing position, while the S-LMA was inserted using the single-handed rotational technique in the semi-sniffing position in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions. The cuff was fully deflated and lubricated. Only size 4 G-LMA or S-LMA was used for adults weighing 50-70kg. Following insertion, the patients' heads were stabilized in the neutral position, and the cuff of the LMA device was air-inflated with a syringe to 60cmH₂O ICP, and this pressure was maintained throughout the surgical procedure using the Ambu Cuff Pressure Gauge (Ambu GmbH, Germany). The volume of air for cuff inflation to 60 cmH₂O was recorded. The LMA device was connected to a breathing circuit system. The effective airway was confirmed by bilateral symmetrical chest movement during manual ventilation, a square wave on capnography, absence of audible air leak from the mouth, and the lack of gastric insufflation [12]. When these criteria were satisfied, the insertion was successful. The number of insertion attempts required for both devices was recorded. If bilateral chest movement was not proper, air leakage through the oral cavity, then the cuff was deflated, and a second attempt was done for the correct placement of either LMA devices. If the second attempt failed, then the patients were excluded from the study, and endotracheal intubation was performed. The insertion time was recorded by an independent observer and defined as the time interval between picking up the prepared devices and securing effective ventilation. The device was fixed by taping the tube over the chin. The anaesthesia was maintained by continuous infusion of propofol (4-6 mg/kg/h) and remifentanyl (0.1-0.3 µg/kg/min). The neuromuscular blockade rocuronium 0.15 mg/kg was administered as required to maintain adequate surgical relaxation. The patients' lungs were ventilated with a tidal volume of 8 ml/kg, an inspiratory: expiratory ratio of 1:2, and the respiratory rate was adjusted according to an end-tidal CO₂ of 35-40 mmHg with a fresh gas flow of 1.5 l/min. All the baseline parameters (heart rate, blood pressure, ETCO₂, and SpO₂) were kept within normal limits until the end of surgery. Once the effective airway was secured, ASP was measured at an ICP of 60 cmH₂O in both the G-LMA and S-LMA groups by closing the expiratory valve of the breathing system at a fixed gas flow rate of 3 L/min and recording the airway pressure (maximum allowed, 40 cmH₂O) at which equilibrium was reached. The test used to detect the airway leak was an audible sound of gas escaping from the mouth, which could be heard by listening closely to the patient's mouth [13]. ICP was measured at 30, 60, 90, and 120 minutes and maintained at 60 cmH₂O until the end of surgery. A well-lubricated gastric tube (14-French size) was inserted into the stomach of each patient through the gastric port. Appropriate tube placement was confirmed by aspiration of gastric contents or by auscultation over the epigastrium while 20 mL of air was injected into the tube [14]. The time elapsed for the proper placement of the tube was recorded. Failure was defined as the inability to advance the gastric tube into the stomach within two attempts. The anatomical position of the device was assessed by inserting the flexible fiber-optic bronchoscope into the airway tube in a position proximal to the terminal end. The fiber-optic score was done as per Table 1 [15, 16]

Table 1 Fiberoptic score.

Score
4 Clear vocal cord visible
3 Vocal cord plus posterior epiglottis visible
2 Vocal cord plus anterior epiglottis visible
1 No vocal cord visible

At the end of surgery, anaesthesia was stopped, and all patients received atropine (0.02-0.04 mg/kg) and neostigmine (0.04-0.08 mg/kg) to reverse the neuromuscular blockade [17]. The S-LMA or G-LMA was removed when spontaneous respiration was established, and the patient was able to open their mouth in response to a verbal command. After removal of the device, blood staining of the device was recorded. The patients were transferred to the post-anaesthetic care unit (PACU) for further monitoring. The patients were asked at 1, 2, and 24 hours after the end of surgery to assess post-operative pharyngolaryngeal adverse events (sore throat, dysphagia, and dysphonia). The predetermined definition of post-operative pharyngolaryngeal adverse events for assessment: sore throat was defined as "constant pain or discomfort in the throat independent of swallowing"; dysphagia was defined as "difficulty or pain provoked by swallowing"; dysphonia was defined as "difficulty or pain in speaking" [13]. These questions were asked by an independent observer.

Statistical analysis

The primary outcome is the airway sealing pressure. The sample size was calculated to be 37 patients per group based on our study with a test power (1-beta) of 80% and an alpha level of 0.05 (for a two-sided test). This gives an estimated difference of 2 cmH₂O between groups, where the mean ± SD of airway sealing pressure of GLMA was 32.06 ± 4.03 cmH₂O and SLMA was 28.09 ± 4.11 cmH₂O - as determined by an intracuff pressure of 60 cmH₂O. In case of any potential dropout, a sample size of 40 patients in each group was selected. The SPSS Statistics 18.0 software version was used for statistical analysis. The variables; LMA insertion time, airway sealing pressure, gastric tube insertion time, ICP measurement, volume of air for cuff inflation to 60 cmH₂O, volume of air added to maintain cuff pressure at 60 cmH₂O were compared using a student's *t*-test and Mann-Whitney test. Successful device insertion attempts, gastric tube insertion attempts, fibreoptic view, and postoperative pharyngolaryngeal adverse events were compared using Chi-square and Fisher exact tests. Significance was taken as a p-value ≤ 0.05.

Results

The data are presented as mean ± SD or number or percentage. There were no significant differences between the patients' characteristics and surgery types in both groups (Table 2).

Table 2 Demographic data and type of surgery performed.

Variables	Group S (S-LMA) (n=40)	Group G (G-LMA) (n=40)	P value
Age (years)	46.80±13.58	45.75±11.62	0.794
Sex (M/F)	10/30	13/27	0.802
Height (cm)	159.50±5.73	162.19±4.56	0.123
Weight (kg)	63.15±5.53	63.15±5.53	0.527
BMI (kg/m ²)	23.54±2.25	23.28±2.61	0.845
Surgery types			
Gynecology	25	16	0.274
Orthopedic	5	11	
Urology	7	7	
General surgery	3	6	

*P < 0.05, S-LMA: Supreme laryngeal mask airway; G-LMA: Guardian laryngeal mask airway.

Table 3 Airway sealing pressure, cuff pressure, and cuff volume.

Variables	Group S (S-LMA) (n=40)	Group G (G-LMA) (n=40)	P value
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Airway sealing pressure (cmH ₂ O)	28.09±4.11*	32.06±4.03*	0.003*
Cuff pressure measurement (cmH ₂ O)			
30 min	58.52±1.40	58.95±1.07	0.272
60 min	58.60±1.40	58.26±1.21	0.327
90 min	58.10±1.48	58.32±1.30	0.589
120 min	58.13±1.36	58.47±1.23	0.469
Volume of air for cuff inflation to 60 cmH ₂ O, ml	25.60±2.45*	22.57±3.17*	0.03*

*P<0.05, S-LMA: Supreme laryngeal mask airway; G-LMA: Guardian laryngeal mask airway; ml: milliliter; min: minutes.

Table 3 shows the results of airway sealing pressure, volume of air for cuff inflation to 60 cmH₂O, and ICP measurement.

Table 4 Insertion characteristics of LMA devices and gastric tube, Fiber-optic score and pharyngolaryngeal adverse events.

Variables	Group S (SLMA) (n=40)	Group G (GLMA) (n=40)	P value
Successful insertion attempts			
First	39 (97.5%)	39 (97.5%)	1.000
Second	1	1	
Device insertion time, (seconds)	13.55±1.67	13.24±1.72	0.530
Successful gastric tube insertion attempts			
First	38 (95%)	38 (95%)	1.000
Second	2	2	
Gastric tube insertion time, seconds	10.90±1.83	10.10±1.21	0.111
Fiber-optic score (n:4/3/2/1)	15/17/6/2	18/19/2/1	0.437
Blood stain	7/40 (17.5%)	9/40 (22.5%)	0.578
Postoperative pharyngolaryngeal adverse events			
Sore throat			
1 h	5/40 (12.5%)	8/40 (20%)	0.366
2 h	5/40(12.5%)	8/40 (20%)	0.366
24 h	0	0	
Dysphagia			
1 h	3/40 (7.5%)	6/40 (15%)	0.291
2 h	3/40 (7.5%)	6/40 (15%)	0.291
24 h	0	0	
Dysphonia			
1 h	0	0	

2 h	0	0	
24 h	0	0	

*P<0.05, S-LMA: Supreme laryngeal mask airway; G-LMA: Guardian laryngeal mask airway; h: hour.

Table 4 shows the results of successful insertion attempts, device insertion time, successful gastric tube insertion attempts, gastric tube insertion time, fiberoptic assessment of position for each airway device, blood staining on removal of the device, and postoperative pharyngolaryngeal adverse events. At 60 cmH₂O ICP, the ASP of G-LMA was significantly higher than that of S-LMA, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1 Guardian laryngeal mask airway

Figure 2 Airway sealing pressure GLMA vs SLMA

The volume of air for cuff inflation was less in G-LMA than S-LMA. We found no differences in ICP measurement, successful insertion attempts of airway devices (97.5% at the first attempt for both devices), device insertion time, successful gastric tube insertion attempts (95% at the first attempt for both devices), gastric tube insertion time, fiberoptic assessment of the position of airway devices, blood staining (G-LMA, 22.5%; S-LMA, 17.5%), and pharyngolaryngeal adverse events (sore throat, dysphagia, and dysphonia) at 1, 2, and 24 hours after the end of surgery. All the baseline parameters like heart rate, blood pressure, ETCO₂, and SpO₂ were comparable between the groups and found within the normal limit during the intraoperative period. The hemodynamic and respiratory responses of patients between the groups were found within the normal limit in the PACU. There was no vomiting, no regurgitation of gastric content, and no trauma like lip/teeth/gum observed in both groups.

Discussion

In this prospective randomized study, we compared the clinical performance of two laryngeal mask airways (G-LMA and S-LMA) and their postoperative pharyngolaryngeal adverse events. We found that the G-LMA had a higher airway sealing pressure (ASP) with similar successful insertion attempts and insertion time of the device as well as gastric tube insertion compared to the S-LMA. The primary outcome was measuring the ASP, which was done when both devices had their cuffs inflated to a pressure of 60 cmH₂O. We found that the mean airway sealing pressure was higher in the G-LMA than in the S-LMA. This may be due to several reasons: first, the structural difference in shape and/or size of the cuff; second, the use of a more tissue-adherent elastic silicone-based device rather than a less elastic PVC-based device; third, the softer airway curved tube allowing full depth of insertion rather than a rigid curved airway tube. The higher ASP indicates airway protection, feasibility of positive pressure ventilation, and successful placement of the devices [12]. At 60 cmH₂O cuff pressure, Verghese C et al. [5] concluded that there is no evidence of a difference in seal pressure between the S-LMA and ProSeal LMA. Hosten T et al. [18] suggested that the S-LMA had leak pressure similar to the ProSeal LMA. Tham H. M et al. [19] reported that the laryngeal seal pressure was similar for both the S-LMA and ProSeal LMA. Hosten T et al. [20] demonstrated that the S-LMA and ProSeal LMA had identical leak pressure during laparoscopic cholecystectomy, suggesting that the G-LMA is a suitable airway device in laparoscopic surgery. A direct comparative study would be required to confirm this. However, Seet et al. [21] claimed that the S-LMA has a lower leak pressure than the ProSeal LMA. The cuffs of all devices were inflated to 60 cmH₂O. We found that the volume required to achieve an intracuff pressure (ICP) of 60 cmH₂O was less in the G-LMA than in the S-LMA. This may be due to the more elastic nature of silicone rather than PVC, which is less elastic, or differences in the shape and volume of the cuff. Van Zundert et al. [22] reported that increased leak pressures with the S-LMA are associated with an increase in ICP. Yet, Zhang et al. [23] claimed that higher leak pressures are achieved with the S-LMA at high ICP. The leak pressure did not change despite an increase in ICP during surgery [18]. To eliminate the potential effect of ICP, we measured ICP at 30, 60, 90, and 120 minutes and found no difference in both groups, maintaining it at 60 cmH₂O pressure throughout the surgery. Several studies reported that the ICP of silicone-based devices increases progressively over time when the breathing gas mixture contains nitrous oxide [24]. Our study did not use nitrous oxide gas during surgery. The LMA manufacturers recommend a maximum ICP of no more than 60 cmH₂O. A higher ICP of the LMA may decrease the pharyngeal mucosal pressure and lead to throat discomfort [25]. Pharyngeal mucosal perfusion is progressively reduced when the cuffed oropharyngeal airway pressure, is increased, resulting in postoperative pharyngolaryngeal adverse events [9]. Therefore, several studies have reported that reducing cuff pressure of LMA devices resulted in fewer pharyngolaryngeal adverse events [10, 26, 27]. Seet et al. demonstrated that using manometry to limit LMA classic ICP to less than 44 mmHg or 60 cmH₂O reduces pharyngolaryngeal adverse events [14], but 60 cmH₂O is still the upper limit for airway perfusion pressure. There is a risk that pressure neuropraxia from the LMA cuff can result in dysphonia [28, 29]. We found no differences in postoperative pharyngolaryngeal adverse events (sore throat, dysphagia, and dysphonia) at 1, 2, and 24 hours between the two groups after surgery. The cause may be associated with postoperative analgesics, which were not recorded in our study and considered a drawback. In our study, we found that the first successful insertion attempt and the mean insertion time were similar in both groups. Despite differences in cuff design and airway tube, both devices are simple, easy to handle, and quick to insert. The successful gastric tube insertion attempt and mean gastric tube insertion time were similar in both groups. Both devices have a drainage tube placed posteriorly to the ventilator side and

running through the midline of the airway tube. We believe that both devices having a similar drainage tube design may explain the easy access of the gastric tube to prevent the aspiration of gastric content. We found no differences in the fiberoptic position of airway devices in both groups. The G-LMA has two additional features that are not present in the S-LMA: the hypopharyngeal port and a visibly built-in intracuff pressure monitor. In our study, the efficacy of these features was not formally tested, but the intracuff pressure roughly matches the handheld pressure measuring device. However, our study does have some drawbacks. We only used size-4 devices in adult patients with a neuromuscular blockade, but it can be presumed that similar results would be obtained in patients who have not received a neuromuscular blockade. The assessment of pharyngolaryngeal adverse events was conducted at multiple time intervals, which may introduce bias. Lastly, some data were not blinded, potentially causing a source of bias.

Conclusion

The Guardian laryngeal mask airway provides a better airway sealing pressure at a cuff pressure of 60 cmH₂O compared to the Supreme laryngeal mask airway in anesthetized adult patients who are receiving neuromuscular blocking drugs. However, both devices performed similarly and can be used in clinical practice.

Conflict of interest

The authors declared that they have no competing interests.

Abbreviation

ASP (Airway Sealing Pressure); G-LMA (Guardian Laryngeal Mask Airway); ICP (Intracuff Pressure); LMA (laryngeal mask airway); PACU (Post Anesthetic Care Unit); S-LMA (Supreme Laryngeal Mask Airway)

Authors' contributions

Ajay Kumar Pajiyar helped design the study, conduct the study, analyze the data and write the initial draft of manuscript. Amit kumar karna help in writing manuscript, and analysis. Lumin Miao recruited the patient, data collection and analysis. Lin Ma recruited the patient, data collection and analysis; Haiyun Wang designed the study, analyzed the data and revised the manuscript. Guolin Wang designed the study and revised the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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